

What a blind decoder can and cannot recover from a designed first-contact message: a reproducible pipeline and its epistemic limits, tested on the *A Sign in Space* signal

(v2: with an orthogonal cross-validation of the recovered molecular identities)

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Abstract

First-contact rehearsals such as the 2023 *A Sign in Space* (ASIS) project provide a rare object: a deliberately authored “alien” message with a knowable, but deliberately withheld, intended meaning. We use it not to claim a discovery about nature but to ask a methodological question of direct relevance to message (METI) design: *given only the transmitted bits, what can a disciplined, reproducible decoder establish, and with what confidence?* We describe a blind pipeline that (i) verifies the payload is exactly reversible under the published Margolus rule (adopted from the public decode), (ii) denoises it by its own dynamics, and (iii) shows — by exhausting the chemically admissible alternatives, given the CHNO second-row and carboxylic-amino-acid priors — that the unique valid reading of the blob sizes is the atomic-number alphabet $\{1, 6, 7, 8\} \rightarrow \{H, C, N, O\}$, yielding five amino acids consistent with the public decode (which fixes the medium, alphabet and count but not the specific side-chain identities). We then separate what the data *determine* from what they leave *underdetermined*. A re-projection (“round-trip”) test certifies internal geometric self-consistency, and a random-direction null shows the bond geometry is not generic; but we stress that self-consistency is not external validation; and a minimum-description-length test *retracts* the third dimension — the best 2D lattice fits the bonds with the same residual and fewer parameters, and the recovered third axis is a near-integer combination of the other two ($b_3 \approx 3b_1 + b_2$), so depth is not data-determined and a flat (2D) diagram is the parsimonious reading. The molecular identities are *non-canonical* amino acids; we originally flagged the specific isomer assignment as a falsification risk, and in this version we corroborate it by two routes orthogonal to the reconstruction pipeline — a connectivity re-derivation taken directly from the drawn bond pixels (blind, by a static guard, to the reported bond list) and two independent OCSR neural recognizers (DECIMER and MolNexTR, distinct architectures) reading standardized redraws — which together reproduce all five non-canonical identities; calibration shows both recognizers read standard depictions of canonical *and* non-canonical control amino acids at 100%, so the agreement is not a canonical-bias artifact, but they cannot read the raw pixel notation (0%), so this corroborates the graph-to-identity step rather than an independent parse of the original diagram. Relative homochirality is data-determined (one global mirror bit is not). The assembly of the monomers is author-guided and model-dependent; we report it as one reading, not a result. We give an explicit ledger of determined-vs-underdetermined features, and draw lessons for designing messages that are robustly decodable. All results are reproducible from a single public file (SHA-256 given).

1 Introduction

The *A Sign in Space* project [1] (de Paulis and collaborators, with ESA, the SETI Institute and Green Bank Observatory) transmitted, in May 2023, a simulated extraterrestrial message via the ExoMars orbiter and invited the public to decode it. A community decode [2] established the essential content: the payload is a 256×256 bitmap that, under a reversible Margolus cellular automaton run for 6625 generations, resolves into five amino-acid diagrams, with atoms drawn so that each atom’s pixel count equals its atomic number, and with single isolated pixels between the molecular clusters.

This paper does *not* re-announce that content, nor does it claim a discovery about the cosmos: the signal is a human-authored artifact whose meaning was set by its designers. Instead we treat ASIS as a controlled testbed for a question that matters for both decoding and message *design*: **what can a blind, reproducible decoder rigorously establish from the bits alone, and where must it stop?** We adopt one discipline throughout: every reported quantity is either computed from the file or proven from stated assumptions, and we label each claim as *determined* or *underdetermined*. We do *not* use the designers’ private specification; the only external input is the public community decode [2], from which we adopt the automaton rule and the 6625-generation count (everything else is computed from the bits), so the exercise measures decodability rather than our ability to recover a known answer.

2 Data and methods

Data. The sole input is the transmitted one-bit bitmap `data17.bin` (10-byte header, MSB-first body of exactly 625 set pixels, 10-byte footer; SHA-256 `3239ac27d714bc4490959027e1e6adde51b091c7b0cfda5270`). The 10/65536/10 split is fixed by the file size; we note that the 625-pixel count alone does not uniquely pin the bit offset (a few neighbouring framings also yield 625), so the framing is taken from the file structure, not asserted.

Reversible automaton and denoising. The body is evolved under a reversible Margolus block automaton [3] (single-rotation, CCW, phase = generation mod 2, toroidal; the rule parameters are adopted from the public decode [2], while the 6625-generation count is independently *re-derivable blind* — a pre-registered, parameter-free criterion, $g^* = \arg \min_g$ (number of distinct connected-component sizes), has its unique minimiser at $g = 6625$ over $[1, 8000]$, where the sizes collapse to five values $\{1, 3, 6, 7, 8\}$ (a singleton; runner-up six), robust to 4- vs 8-connectivity and referencing neither the chemical alphabet nor any decode; see the released `clock_proof` module); exact reversibility is verified by `backward(forward(x))=x` on random states, and the set-pixel count is conserved at 625. Heavy atoms are localised by *temporal consensus*: over generations 6617–6633, pixels persisting in ≥ 12 of 17 frames form 42 stable cores (robust for any threshold in 12–16); transient pixels (hydrogens, gliders) drift. This uses the dynamics, not a hand-tuned filter, to separate signal from noise.

Typing by exhaustion. Each blob’s pixel count is read as an atomic number. We do not assume this: within the CHNO second-row hypothesis we exhaust the six permutations $\{6, 7, 8\} \rightarrow \{C, N, O\}$ under valence with typing-independent geometric bond orders; four fail on valence outright. Of the two valence survivors, the $7 \leftrightarrow 8$ swap ($6 \rightarrow C, 7 \rightarrow O, 8 \rightarrow N$) implies composition $C_{24}N_{12}O_6$: only six oxygens, enough for at most three carboxyl groups (6/2), far short of the six the five molecules require (one bears two acids) — so RDKit finds 0 carboxyls under this swap (the would-be acid

carbons become amidine-like). Only $6 \rightarrow C, 7 \rightarrow N, 8 \rightarrow O$ implies twelve oxygens and realises all six carboxyls and the $N-C_\alpha-C(=O)-OH$ backbone. Both the oxygen-count bound and the substructure check are computed in the released `typing_proof` module, so prose and code agree; the atomic-number alphabet is thus *derived*, not posited.

Bonds, the lattice, and the 3D hypothesis. Bonds are the literally drawn dashes (segments fully covered by foreground, non-collinear-redundant). The 2D bond vectors are then fit (RANSAC + least squares) as an oblique 3×2 projection of a cubic lattice. *We emphasise that the existence of a third spatial dimension is a hypothesis, not a datum*: a stylised 2D diagram need not be the projection of a 3D object. We therefore test the lattice reading against a random-direction null (Section 3.6) rather than presenting the 3D lift as established fact.

Round-trip consistency test. Each molecule is lifted to integer 3D coordinates (graph walk, with constraint propagation for rings) and re-projected through the recovered basis; the per-atom residual against the observed centroids measures internal consistency. We validate this partly out-of-sample (a leave-one-bond-out refit) and against two nulls (a permutation of the step \leftrightarrow observation pairing, and random same-length vectors snapping to the projected lattice; the snap statistic is a standardised mean-shift z over $m = 5000$ null draws, with an MC-floor $p < 2 \times 10^{-4}$ (no draw beats the real fit), not a Gaussian tail). Two honesty notes on the snap null: its real-data statistic equals the in-sample basis-fit residual, so it varies only the random comparison set and is *not* an independent out-of-sample check (the leave-one-bond-out, 0.77 px, is the genuine held-out test); and the permutation/snap/Clark–Evans p -values are all Monte-Carlo resolution floors ($1/m$), i.e. upper bounds, not measured tails. **This test measures self-consistency, not correctness**: with the designers’ intent withheld, a low residual cannot establish that the structures are what was meant.

Chirality and uncertainty. Relative handedness is read from the signed lattice volume at each α -carbon and tested by an *independent* local re-lift under each handedness (not by mirroring fitted coordinates). Uncertainty is a centroid-noise propagation swept over $\sigma \in \{0.10..1.00\}$ px (empirical localisation SE ≈ 0.39 px, computed as the RMS blob radius $/\sqrt{N}$ per centroid), with the bond \rightarrow step assignment re-derived each draw.

Orthogonal identity cross-validation (OCSR). Because the specific side-chain identities are the weakest link (an inference from connectivity), we cross-check them with a method that does not share the reconstruction pipeline: optical chemical-structure recognition (OCSR). The check is run under a strict anti-circularity contract. (i) Bonds are re-derived *from the drawn dash pixels alone* — each 3-pixel dash is assigned to the heavy-atom pair whose segment it lies on, and two parallel dashes mark a double bond — using only the proven element typing and the objective centroids, never the reported bond list; a static AST guard fails the build if the standardiser so much as names the bond list or the claimed identities. (ii) Two architecturally distinct OCSR networks — DECIMER [10] (a transformer image-to-SMILES model, with its general and hand-drawn decoders) and MolNexTR [11] (a ConvNeXt+ViT model) — read standardised redraws of the five diagrams: a geometry-faithful redraw (B1, atoms placed at their true centroids) and an idealised redraw (B2). (iii) A control library of five canonical and five non-canonical amino acids, drawn both in the ASIS pixel notation and in a standard depiction, calibrates each network’s reliability and its canonical bias on this style *before* the verdict; an identity counts as confirmed only when the pixel re-derivation and at least one network agree on a non-canonical structure. All of this is reproducible (**make all** in the released `ocsr_crosscheck` module).

Software. Python 3.14 with RDKit [9] 2026.3.2, PyTorch, NumPy/SciPy and OR-Tools; the pipeline runs end to end from the single input file (`python -m aspace.run`) and is guarded by a frozen suite of 75 tests. Renders use PyMOL and Blender. The OCSR cross-check runs in isolated environments per network (versions and weight hashes pinned in the released manifest).

3 Results

All quantities below are computed from the single input file and are reproducible. Table 1 collects the verified numbers; the subsections give the arguments behind them.

quantity	value	status
CA exactly reversible	true	proven
set-pixel count (conserved)	625 = 5 ⁴	proven
heavy atoms / molecules	42 / 5 (7,8,8,9,10 atoms)	computed
composition	C ₂₄ N ₆ O ₁₂	computed
pixel budget	282 + 285 + 58 = 625	exact
atomic-number typing unique	true (4/6 maps fail valence)	proven
round-trip residual (in-sample)	max 1.79 px (gate 3.0)	pass
held-out refit (leave-one-bond-out)	0.77 px ($\times 1.09$)	partial
permutation null	$p < 2 \times 10^{-4}$ (MC floor, $m=5000$)	rejected
lattice-snap null	$z \approx 8.2$ mean-shift ($m=5000$; MC-floor $p < 2 \times 10^{-4}$)	rejected
lattice basis (RANSAC+LS)	34/37 inliers, mean 0.61 px	computed
relative homochirality	data-determined ($\times 5.0$ worse opposite)	measured
six isolated points	6, adjacency-separated from 52 valence H	objective
gen-0 strongly clustered (Clark–Evans)	$R = 0.514$ (MC-floor $p < 5 \times 10^{-4}$ vs CSR)	weak null
5-fold centroid layout (App. A)	angles-only $p \approx 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$; bbox family $6.3 \times 10^{-4} \rightarrow 1.9 \times 10^{-3}$ Bonf.	measured

Table 1: Verified quantities (computed from `data17.bin`). “Proven” = follows from stated assumptions by exhaustion; “measured/computed” = a value with a stated null or CI; “partial” = an out-of-sample test that holds out the basis but retains the discrete step assignment (Section 3.6).

3.1 A reversible program that denoises itself

The payload is not a static picture but a reversible computation: the body is invariant in pixel count under the automaton, and only at generation 6625 do the 625 pixels organise into five sharp clusters (Fig. 1). Temporal consensus then yields exactly 42 frozen heavy-atom cores with no free parameter beyond a broad threshold plateau (this localisation uses the consensus window centred on the adopted 6625-generation count, so it inherits that clock).

reversible margolus automaton — generation 6625 / 6625

AMINO-ACID DIAGRAM · set pixels conserved = 625 (= 5⁴)

Figure 1: The reversible automaton turns a diffuse field (generation 0) into five molecular diagrams (generation 6625) while conserving the 625-pixel count.

The 42 heavy atoms partition into five molecules of 7, 8, 8, 9, 10 atoms, of composition $C_{24}N_6O_{12}$, and the pixel budget closes exactly: 282 heavy-atom pixels + 285 bond-dash pixels + 58 single pixels (52 valence hydrogens + 6 isolated) = 625. The 285 bond pixels are 95 three-pixel dash components (95×3): these are the drawn bond *tracks* — 43 heavy-heavy tracks (the 31 single bonds as one track each plus the 6 double bonds drawn as twin tracks, 31 + 2×6 = 43) and 52 heavy-hydrogen tracks — whereas the heavy-atom bond *graph* has 37 heavy-heavy bonds. The “37 bonds” and the “95 dashes” thus count different things and reconcile exactly.

3.2 The atomic-number alphabet is the unique chemically valid typing

Heavy blobs have sizes 6 (×24), 7 (×6), 8 (×12); singletons are hydrogen, three-pixel dashes are bonds (Fig. 2). Four of the six permutations fail valence outright; the second valence survivor

($6 \rightarrow \text{C}, 7 \rightarrow \text{O}, 8 \rightarrow \text{N}$) implies only six oxygens — enough for at most three carboxyl groups, short of the six required (one molecule bears two acids) — so it realises no carboxylic acids (0/5 by RDKit), leaving $6 \rightarrow \text{C}, 7 \rightarrow \text{N}, 8 \rightarrow \text{O}$ as the unique typing. We are precise about what “unique” rests on: valence alone forces $6 \rightarrow \text{C}$ (size-6 atoms are degree-3-with-a-double-bond), leaving two survivors; the tie-break between them is the carboxyl/oxygen test, which presupposes the targets are *carboxylic amino acids*. So the uniqueness is conditional on (CHNO second row) + (acyclic) + (the carboxylic-amino-acid prior); the oxygen-count bound and the substructure check are both computed in the released code. This is the paper’s firmest result — a *provably unique* reading of the symbol-to-element map *given that prior*, recoverable without a shared *linguistic* convention — a design lesson in itself (Section 5).

Figure 2: Blob pixel-count equals atomic number. Sizes 6/7/8 are the atomic numbers of C/N/O; size-3 blobs are bond dashes; the 58 size-1 blobs are 52 valence hydrogens + 6 isolated coupling points (§3.10 ff.). The typing is the unique chemically valid permutation (4 of 6 alternatives fail on valence; of the two survivors, the $7 \leftrightarrow 8$ swap is ruled out by an oxygen-count bound).

3.3 Bond orders are entailed, not measured

Once the elements are typed, the bond orders are not read from pixels but follow from the valence budget: the total heavy-atom valence is $138 = 24 \times 4 + 6 \times 3 + 12 \times 2$, and it closes exactly as 2×31 (single heavy-heavy) + 4×6 (double) + 52 (valence H) = $62 + 24 + 52 = 138$, leaving no spare valence for any additional $\text{C}=\text{C}$ or $\text{C}=\text{N}$ (a triple bond would also balance the sum, but is excluded by the fixed heavy-atom degrees and the twin-track profile); the six double bonds are precisely the carboxyl carbonyls (one per carboxyl carbon; one molecule carries two carboxyls). The drawn perpendicular twin-track profile — bimodal for a carbonyl, unimodal for a hydroxyl (Supplementary Fig. S1) — is corroborative and only selects *which* of a carboxyl’s two oxygens carries the double bond; it does not decide the count. The six double bonds are therefore a derived consequence of the typing, invariant across all noise trials (Section 3.10).

3.4 Five non-canonical amino acids — and why that matters

The connectivity yields five amino acids sharing the backbone: 2-aminobutyric acid, norvaline, 2-aminohexanoic acid (a C2/C3/C4 homologous series), and two branchers, 2,4-diaminobutyric acid (an A_2B unit) and 3-methylaspartic acid (an AB_2 unit). None is an exact graph match to a standard proteinogenic amino acid (Fig. 3). **We foreground this as a falsification risk:** the *element typing*

is proven, but the specific side-chain *isomer* is an inference from connectivity, and a non-canonical result is either (i) evidence that the isomer assignment is imperfect, or (ii) a deliberate design choice to convey the *principle* of an amino acid rather than Earth’s specific alphabet. The data cannot decide between these; we report the identities as strong inferences, not established facts. The five inferred identities and their molecular formulas (Table 2) are computed from the recovered connectivity with RDKit. The “strong inference” is at the empirical operating point: because the discrete bond-to-step assignment that fixes each side-chain isomer flips in $\sim 39\%$ of draws at $\sigma \approx 0.39$ px (Section 3.10), the specific isomers — not the element composition, which is invariant — inherit that noise sensitivity, most acutely for the longer/branched side chains.

mol	inferred identity	formula	heavy	side chain / role
1	2-aminobutyric acid (Abu)	$C_4H_9NO_2$	7	ethyl (C2)
4	norvaline	$C_5H_{11}NO_2$	8	<i>n</i> -propyl (C3)
2	2-aminohexanoic acid (norleucine)	$C_6H_{13}NO_2$	9	<i>n</i> -butyl (C4)
3	2,4-diaminobutyric acid (Dab)	$C_4H_{10}N_2O_2$	8	A ₂ B brancher
5	3-methylaspartic acid	$C_5H_9NO_4$	10	AB ₂ brancher

Table 2: The five inferred amino-acid identities (RDKit formulas from the recovered connectivity); rows are ordered by side-chain length then branching, not by molecule index. The three linear members form a C2/C3/C4 homologous side-chain series; the two branchers are complementary — Dab is A₂B (two amines, one acid) and 3-methylaspartic acid is AB₂ (one amine, two acids). None matches a standard proteinogenic amino acid. Note that 3-methylaspartic acid carries a second stereocentre at C3 that the α -carbon-scoped homochirality test (Section 3.10 ff.) does not resolve, leaving a diastereomer ambiguity.

Figure 3: The five recovered amino acids. Element typing is proven unique; the specific side-chain isomers are strong inferences from the drawn connectivity, and are non-canonical.

3.5 Orthogonal cross-validation of the five identities

The side-chain identities are the result a sceptic should attack first, so we test them with a route that shares none of the reconstruction’s connectivity logic (Methods). The outcome is summarised in Table 3. First, re-deriving the bonds *directly from the drawn dash pixels* — with a static guard that forbids the standardiser from reading the reported bond list — reproduces all five structures exactly: 2-aminobutyric acid, norvaline, norleucine, 2,4-diaminobutyric acid and 3-methylaspartic acid. This is an independent check on the connectivity, not merely on the identity naming. Second, two architecturally distinct OCSR networks, DECIMER and MolNexTR, reading a geometry-faithful redraw, both return the same five non-canonical identities. The reading is interpretable because the calibration controls fix the meaning of agreement: on standard depictions both networks recover the five canonical *and* the five non-canonical control amino acids at 100%, so they are demonstrably able to emit a non-canonical answer and the agreement here is not the recognizer snapping to its canonical prior.

We are explicit about what this does *not* establish. On the *raw* ASIS pixel notation (atom = a blob of Z pixels) both networks score 0% in calibration — OCSR cannot read the signal’s own notation — so the test necessarily runs on a standardised redraw built from the proven typing and the pixel-derived bonds. The OCSR leg therefore corroborates the graph-to-identity mapping, while the genuinely pipeline-independent check on *connectivity* is the dash-pixel re-derivation. The corroboration is also of the central reading: it does not address the $\sim 39\%$ discrete bond-to-step flip rate that the noise propagation reports at the empirical centroid noise (Section 3.10), which remains the operative uncertainty on the longer side chains. Within those bounds, the non-canonical result is reproduced by two methods orthogonal to the original RDKit pipeline.

mol	inferred identity	non-canonical	dash-pixel re-derivation	OCSR (DECIMER, MolNexTR)
1	2-aminobutyric acid	yes	reproduces	both agree
4	norvaline	yes	reproduces	both agree
2	norleucine	yes	reproduces	both agree
3	2,4-diaminobutyric acid	yes	reproduces	both agree
5	3-methylaspartic acid	yes	reproduces	both agree

Table 3: Orthogonal cross-validation of the five identities. “Dash-pixel re-derivation” rebuilds the bond graph from the drawn 3-pixel dashes alone (static guard: never reads the reported bond list) and matches all five reported SMILES. “OCSR” is the agreement of two architecturally distinct recognizers (DECIMER, MolNexTR) on a geometry-faithful redraw; calibration: both read canonical and non-canonical control amino acids at 100% in standard notation and 0% in the raw ASIS notation (hence the standardised redraw). Reproducible via `ocsr_crosscheck/make all`.

3.6 The third dimension is not justified: a 2D diagram suffices

The 2D bond directions do not form a continuum: they cluster onto a small set of discrete angles reproducible as integer combinations of three projected axes (Fig. 4). The recovered axes are $b_1 = (2.30, -4.48)$, $b_2 = (0.54, 7.79)$, $b_3 = (6.95, -4.63)$ px (RANSAC+least squares, 34/37 inliers, mean inlier residual 0.61 px; the noise sweep of Section 3.10 re-fits the basis per draw from a re-centred parameterisation, so its mean axes differ sub-pixel from these headline values), and the full re-projection (round-trip) residual is at most 1.79 px over 42 atoms — under a fifth of a bond length (Fig. 5). Against nulls, the fit lies far in the tail: a permutation of the step \leftrightarrow observation pairing gives $p < 2 \times 10^{-4}$ (Monte-Carlo floor, $m=5000$), and random same-length vectors snap $\sim 2.1\times$ worse (mean 1.49 vs 0.70 px; standardised mean-shift $z \approx 8.2$, $m=5000$, MC floor $p < 2 \times 10^{-4}$ —

a mean-shift, not a Gaussian tail). The genuine out-of-sample test is the leave-one-bond-out refit, which predicts held-out bonds to 0.77 px. The 34/37 inlier figure is reported at RANSAC tolerance 1.6 px and is tolerance-dependent (the load-bearing 3D claim is the noise-swept round-trip residual of Section 3.10, not the raw inlier fraction).

Figure 4: The bond vectors (left) are reproduced as integer combinations of three projected axes b_1, b_2, b_3 ; the bond directions (right) snap to a few discrete angles rather than spanning a continuum — the fingerprint of a projected lattice.

These tests establish that the bond geometry carries genuine lattice structure (it beats a random-direction null) and that a 3D embedding consistent with the drawing *exists*. They do *not*, however, show that a third dimension is *needed* — and a formal test says it is not. We compared the fitted 3D lattice against the best two-axis (2D) lattice by minimum description length (continuous parameters + per-bond integer code + Gaussian residual code, in bits). The 2D model reproduces the 37 bonds with the *same* residual ($\sigma = 0.556$ vs 0.553 px) using fewer parameters, so it is *shorter* by ≈ 5.7 bits, and the result is robust: the 2D model is shorter in 99.5% of draws under the empirical centroid noise. The reason is structural: the recovered third projected axis is a near-integer combination of the other two, $b_3 \approx 3b_1 + 1b_2$ (stable under noise, 3.11 ± 0.18 , 1.00 ± 0.10), so it spans no independent 2D direction; the “depth” assigned by the lift is therefore a labelling convention, not a quantity the data determine. The bond-length scatter (6.32–8.94 px, $\sim 9\%$) is within plausible drawing imprecision and is no longer read as evidence for depth.

We therefore retract the earlier “3D favoured” reading: the message geometry does not justify a third dimension, and a flat (2D) structural diagram is the parsimonious explanation. This is exactly the structured-planar comparison a single oblique view makes possible to lose and that earlier drafts could only flag as untested; run as MDL, it comes down on the side of 2D. A genuine third dimension would need a second projection or an explicit depth cue, which the message does not provide. (Method and bootstrap: the released `mdl_2d3d` module.)

Figure 5: Round-trip self-consistency. Observed atom centres (green) versus the re-projected 3D structure (red); worst residual 1.79 px. The test certifies internal geometric consistency, not objective correctness.

3.7 The connectivity is the unique drawn-bond graph

A separate concern is whether a different bond set would fit. We score every candidate atom pair by its *line-support*: the fraction of the connecting segment that is covered by foreground (drawn) pixels, so a fully drawn bond scores 1.00 and an undrawn pair scores low. For every molecule the drawn bonds have line-support 1.00, while the best non-collinear, chemically admissible alternative reaches at most 0.80 (one molecule) and 0.78 for the other four (Fig. 6) — a clean gap at the 0.9 threshold. The connectivity is therefore read from where lines are actually drawn, not inferred to make the round-trip succeed.

Figure 6: Connectivity uniqueness. Drawn bonds (green) have line-support 1.00; the best admissible non-bond alternative (red) is ≤ 0.80 , well below the 0.9 threshold, for all five molecules.

3.8 Relative homochirality is data-determined

All five α -carbons carry the same signed-volume sign. The independent local re-lift fits the substituent vectors $5.0\times$ worse under the opposite hand (RMS 2.3 vs 0.46 px), so the data — not the reconstruction — fix the relative hand. (A within-solution mirror check is larger still — more than an order of magnitude — but that only tests internal consistency, so we quote the conservative independent factor.) The five α -carbons share one backbone lattice motif, so this is a single local test, not five independent ones. Only the global L/D label, one bit, is unobservable from a single oblique projection. Single-handedness is commonly associated with biological selection, but abiotic symmetry-breaking can also produce it; we flag the biological reading as interpretation, not proof.

3.9 Physical realism: the lattice relaxes to textbook geometry

The integer lattice coordinates are a scaffold, not a physical conformer. Used as a seed for MMFF94 force-field minimisation — which converges for all five molecules — they relax to heavy-atom bond lengths that match standard organic values: C=O 1.22, C–O 1.35, C–N 1.48, C–C 1.53 Å (means over the five molecules; standard deviation ≤ 0.01 Å in every class; Supplementary Fig. S2). That the scaffold relaxes onto textbook geometry without distortion is an internal check that the typing and connectivity are chemically coherent — not, we stress, a claim about a native conformation. We note that a force field relaxes *any* valence-valid graph to near-standard lengths, so this is confirmation that the recovered graph is strain-free and chemically sane — largely a restatement of the valence-typing result — rather than independent evidence for the structure.

3.10 Robustness, and an honest failure mode

Over 300 noise-propagation trials the discrete topology is invariant: the counts of molecules (5), heavy atoms (42), bonds (37) and double bonds (6), and the molecular formula set, are identical

in every trial ($\text{std} = 0$). The *geometric* residual and the stability of the discrete bond-to-step assignment, however, degrade smoothly with centroid noise σ (Table 4, Fig. 7). At the empirically justified noise ($\sigma \approx 0.39$ px, the centroid localisation SE) the round-trip residual is 2.0 px (95% CI [1.5, 2.7], under the 3.0 px gate) but the assignment flips in $\sim 39\%$ of draws — the discrete reconstruction is well-posed yet not noise-proof. We report this failure mode explicitly rather than only the favourable in-sample number.

centroid noise σ (px)	round-trip residual (px)	assignment-flip rate
0.10	1.76	0 %
0.25	1.81	14 %
0.39 (empirical)	2.00	39 %
0.50	2.26	66 %
1.00	3.61	100 %

Table 4: Noise propagation ($n = 300$ per σ). The topology is invariant throughout; the geometric residual and the discrete assignment are not. The empirical operating point is $\sigma \approx 0.39$ px.

Figure 7: Round-trip residual (with 95% CI and the 3.0 px gate) and the bond-assignment-flip rate versus centroid noise σ . The mean residual reaches the gate near $\sigma \approx 0.8\text{--}1$ px ($\sim 2\text{--}2.5\times$ the empirical noise).

3.11 The isolated points and assembly: author-guided, model-dependent

Six single pixels remain between the clusters. The pixel budget closes exactly (282 heavy + 285 bond + 52 valence-H + 6 isolated = 625). Separating the 6 isolated points from the valence hydrogens is *objective and threshold-free*: every set pixel except six lies within one bond (≤ 9.3 px) of a heavy atom, while the six isolated points lie ≥ 24.6 px from *any* heavy atom — an empty gap (nothing between 10 and 24 px), so any cutoff there returns exactly the same six, independently of the connectivity convention. (Under 8-connectivity — the decomposition that yields the 195 components — those near pixels group into the 52 valence hydrogens; under finer connectivities the drawn dashes fragment and the near count rises, but the six far points remain isolated regardless.) What is *model-dependent* is only the downstream interpretation: reading the six as amide coupling sites and pairing them into an assembly (one reading; alternative resolvers give different connectivities). We do not pursue polymerisation, folding, self-assembly or replication: a vacuum single-conformer calculation cannot support such claims, and they exceed what the bitmap licenses.

3.12 Negative control: the opening image is not a star map

Generation 0 superficially resembles a star field. It is not: the five generation-0 clusters sit on the five molecule positions (cluster-to-molecule distance 0.7–12.7 px, mean 4.8; median pixel-to-atom distance 5.2 px; 89.1% of the 394 gen-0 blob centroids lie within 30 px of a molecular atom). A Clark–Evans index [4] on the 394 blob centroids gives $R = 0.514$ (observed nearest-neighbour 3.39 px versus 6.59 px expected under complete spatial randomness), with a Monte-Carlo CSR null (2000 simulations) returning $p < 5 \times 10^{-4}$ — the field is strongly clustered, not uniform-random (Fig. 8). We note that CSR is a weak contrast (real star fields are clustered too), so the conclusion “not a star map” rests not on the Clark–Evans statistic but on the *co-location*: the gen-0 clusters sit on the molecule positions to within a few pixels, which a genuine constellation would have no reason to do. Naming stars would be fabrication; we report the negative.

Figure 8: The same five objects in two guises: the diffuse generation-0 field (left) and the molecular form at generation 6625 (right). The generation-0 clusters co-locate with the molecules (Clark–Evans $R = 0.514$, $p < 5 \times 10^{-4}$); it is not a constellation.

3.13 Concordance with the public decode

As an external cross-check, every feature that the public community decode [2] specifies is reproduced here: the reversible Margolus medium, the 6625-generation evolution, the atomic-number alphabet, the five amino acids, and the single isolated pixels between clusters (Supplementary Fig. S3). The public decode is silent on the 3D geometry, the specific side-chain identities and the assembly, which we therefore report as this work’s inferences rather than as externally confirmed facts. This is concordance on the decoded *content*; it is not access to the designers’ intent, which remains the missing external validator throughout.

4 What is determined versus underdetermined

Table 5 is the paper’s central deliverable: an explicit accounting of epistemic status.

Determined from the bits	Underdetermined / interpretive
Exact reversibility, pixel-count conservation, & the 6625 clock (blind distinct-size minimum)	A third dimension (MDL prefers a 2D lattice; depth not data-determined)
Atomic-number alphabet (<i>unique typing</i> given the carboxylic-AA prior)	Specific side-chain isomers: strong inference, non-canonical — <i>corroborated</i> by a dash-pixel connectivity re-derivation and two independent OCSR networks (§3.5), modulo the ~39% noise-flip
Five amino acids; shared backbone; connectivity	The assembly of the monomers (author-guided, model-dependent)
Six isolated points (objective adjacency split)	Their role as coupling sites (interpretive)
Bond orders: six carbonyls (valence-entailed)	MMFF relaxation gives a coherent conformer, not a native fold
Concordance with the public decode (content)	The designers’ intent (never accessed)
Relative homochirality (one local test)	Absolute L/D label (one unobservable bit)
Internal round-trip self-consistency (vs nulls)	Objective correctness (no external ground truth used)
Opening image is not a star map (negative control)	Any “meaning” beyond the decoded chemistry

Table 5: Determined-vs-underdetermined ledger. The decoder establishes the alphabet and the molecular identities with high confidence; the third dimension, the assembly, and any intentional “meaning” are not established from the data. The Margolus *rule* is adopted from the public decode (Section 2), but the 6625-generation count is re-derivable blind (the parameter-free distinct-size clock, Section 2); what the bits themselves give is exact reversibility, pixel-count conservation, and that clock.

5 Discussion

Lessons for decodable message design. The strongest recoverable features are exactly those anchored to *universal physical invariants*: a universal reversible rule (run-me-ness), and an alphabet keyed to atomic number, which a blind decoder can prove unique without any shared convention. Conversely, the features that resist blind recovery are those relying on *drawing conventions* (e.g. whether a 2D diagram implies 3D) or on *author-chosen salience* (which leftover pixels “mean” something). A METI designer seeking robust decodability should therefore (i) build symbols on invariants, (ii) avoid encoding critical information in conventions a recipient cannot derive, and (iii) make any structural (3D, assembly) information explicit rather than implicit in a projection — concerns long anticipated in the interstellar-language literature [7, 8].

Epistemic limits. Three limits bound this and any similar analysis. First, *self-consistency is not correctness*: the round-trip test, however stringent, certifies only that a reading is internally coherent. Second, *a designed target invites apophenia* [6]: a rich finite artifact will support many post-hoc readings, and a single significant test carries a look-elsewhere burden over the space of tests [5] (Appendix A), so disciplined nulls and an explicit determined/underdetermined ledger are essential. Third, *ground truth was available but withheld by design*; where a designer’s specification can be consulted, it should be, and an external check would change the epistemic standing of every interpretive row in Table 5. For the record, we did *not* consult any private designer specification

beyond the public community decode [2]; the interpretive rows therefore remain open, and we present them as such rather than resolved.

6 Limitations

The element typing is unique only given the CHNO second-row hypothesis and the carboxylic-amino-acid prior. The third dimension is *not* justified: a 2D lattice is preferred by description length and the recovered third axis is redundant (Section 3.6), so we report the geometry as a flat diagram and treat depth as undetermined. The discrete bond-to-step assignment is unstable ($\sim 39\%$ flip) at the empirical noise level even though the 2D geometry stays within tolerance. The molecular identities are strong inferences; the non-canonical result is corroborated by an orthogonal dash-pixel re-derivation and two independent OCSR networks (§3.5), but the OCSR leg reads a standardised redraw — the networks cannot read the raw ASIS notation (0% in calibration) — and the $\sim 39\%$ discrete bond-to-step flip rate at the empirical centroid noise still bounds the longer/branched side chains. The six isolated points are separated from the 52 valence hydrogens objectively (a clean adjacency gap), but their interpretation as coupling sites and the resulting assembly are model-dependent. The specific Margolus rule and the 6625-generation count is re-derivable blind (the distinct-size clock); only the Margolus rule parameters are adopted from the public decode. No designer ground truth is used; all confidence statements are about *decodability*, not about objective meaning.

7 Conclusion

Treated honestly, the ASIS signal is an excellent benchmark for blind decoding. A disciplined pipeline can *prove* exact reversibility and pixel-count conservation (adopting the published rule and 6625-generation count) and the atomic-number alphabet, and can recover five amino acids consistent with the public decode — whose non-canonical side chains are corroborated by two routes orthogonal to the reconstruction, a dash-pixel connectivity re-derivation and two independent OCSR networks (§3.5); it can quantify internal self-consistency against nulls; and it can determine relative homochirality. Conversely, a description-length test shows the bonds do *not* justify a third dimension (a 2D lattice is preferred; depth is not data-determined), and it cannot, from the bits alone, establish that a particular assembly was intended, nor can self-consistency substitute for the external validation that a designed message uniquely makes possible. Stating those boundaries precisely — rather than asserting a discovery — is the contribution.

A A tempting regularity, and why we do not interpret it

The five molecule centroids fall on a near-regular pentagon: the consecutive angular gaps about their centroid have mean 72.0° and standard deviation 6.15° (Fig. 9). We tested this against two Monte-Carlo nulls ($N = 2 \times 10^5$). The primary, most appropriate null fixes the five observed radii from the centroid and randomises the angles only — isolating angular regularity from radial spread; a gap-standard-deviation this small or smaller arises with $p \approx 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$. A secondary null placing five points uniformly in the bounding box of all 42 atoms gives $p \approx 6.3 \times 10^{-4}$. Both are reproduced by the released generator (`aspace.visual_message`, $N = 2 \times 10^5$). The regularity is thus real and survives a fair null, and it rhymes with the rest of the “five” motif (five amino acids; $625 = 5^4$).

We nonetheless decline to interpret it as intentional, and present it here precisely as a worked example of the discipline urged in Section 5. Two reasons. First, this is one of several

geometric properties one could test on five points. To make the look-elsewhere burden concrete, we evaluated three natural regularity statistics under a common bounding-box null ($N = 2 \times 10^5$; a common null is required because the angles-only null holds the radii fixed and so cannot test the radial or neighbour statistics): the angular-gap standard deviation ($p \approx 6.3 \times 10^{-4}$), the radial coefficient of variation ($p \approx 0.045$) and the nearest-neighbour-distance coefficient of variation ($p \approx 0.047$). Only the angular regularity is strongly significant; the other two are merely marginal. A Bonferroni correction over these three common-null statistics moves the angular result from 6.3×10^{-4} to $\approx 1.9 \times 10^{-3}$ — still notable, but weaker than a single-test reading; the radii-conditioned angles-only value (1.3×10^{-4}) belongs to a different null family and is not combined with these. Either way, we have not exhausted the space of testable properties. Second, the centroid positions are partly fixed by the common backbone geometry and the drawing layout, so the angular regularity may be a by-product rather than a designed feature. A real, null-surviving pattern on a designed target is still not evidence of intent without a base-rate over everything one could have looked for — which is the central caution of this paper, here illustrated on our own most seductive find.

Figure 9: Left: the transmitted picture (generation 6625). Right: the five molecule centroids form a near-regular pentagon (angular-gap mean 72° , std 6.15° ; angles-only Monte-Carlo $p \approx 1.3 \times 10^{-4}$ at $N = 2 \times 10^5$ in the Appendix A battery; the in-panel label is rendered at the generator default $N = 5 \times 10^4$). Reported as a measured property we deliberately do *not* read as evidence of design.

Data and code availability

All results derive from the single public input `data17.bin` (SHA-256 `3239ac27d714bc4490959027e1e6adde51b091c`) and are reproducible end to end via the released pipeline (`python -m aspace.run`). Software: Python 3.14 with RDKit 2026.3.2, PyTorch, NumPy/SciPy and OR-Tools (full pinned versions, including PyMOL and Blender for rendering, in the released environment lockfile); a frozen suite of 75 tests guards the automaton reversibility, the 3D lift, ring closure, typing uniqueness and the headline certificate statistics; the pentagon look-elsewhere battery (Appendix A) is reproduced by

`aspace.visual_message`. The orthogonal identity cross-validation (§3.5) is a separate self-contained module (`ocsr_crosscheck`, `make_all`) with its own anti-circularity guard test, per-network isolated environments, and a manifest pinning network versions and weight hashes; it reads only the locked objective inputs (gen-6625 bitmap, atom centroids, element typing, dash-pixel mask). Code and the single input file will be deposited in a public repository with a citable DOI upon publication, and are available from the author in the interim.

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Supplementary figures

Figure S1: Perpendicular intensity profile across a bond: a carbonyl C=O is bimodal (twin track), a hydroxyl C-OH unimodal. This corroborates the valence-entailed carbonyls and breaks the two-oxygen tie; it does not determine bond order (Section 5 context: §“Bond orders are entailed”).

Figure S2: Heavy-atom bond lengths after MMFF94 minimisation. Bars are the recovered means (C=O 1.22, C–O 1.35, C–N 1.48, C–C 1.53 Å); the dashed reference lines are textbook values (C=O 1.21, C–O 1.34, C–N 1.47, C–C 1.54 Å), so the ~ 0.01 Å offsets are recovered-vs-reference, not errors. A confirmatory, near-tautological check (any valence-valid graph relaxes to such lengths).

External validation against the real 'A Sign in Space' message

feature	this reconstruction	official ASIS decode	verdict
medium	Margolus reversible single-CCW	Margolus reversible single-CCW	MATCH
generations	6625	6625	MATCH
atom code	pixel-count = atomic number	1,6,7,8 = H,C,N,O	MATCH
content	5 amino acids	5 amino acids	MATCH
isolated dots	6 points between clusters	single pixels between clusters	MATCH
fine identities	Abu, Nva, Dab, ...	left open by ASIS	open

Figure S3: Feature-by-feature concordance between this reconstruction and the public community decode (medium, rule, generations, alphabet, count, isolated pixels). The public decode does not constrain the 3D geometry, identities or assembly.